

Adversities and Coping Mechanisms of Education Students During Online Learning

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Abstract:

Online learning revolutionized education, offering flexibility and accessibility, but challenges students, impacting academic advancement, emotional well-being, and overall college journey. This study utilized a descriptive quantitative method wherein it explored the adversities students face during online learning and their coping mechanisms that involved collecting numerical data and employing analysis. This study examined the hardships students encounter and the strategies they used to navigate these adversities. Participants in this study are college students from 1st year to 3rd-year students from the School of Education in the local college. The result of this study revealed that the most significant source of stress for students in the field of education in online learning is academic workload; it indicates that these students experienced higher stress levels due to the heavy burden of assignments, exams, and deadlines. Conversely, social media emerged as the most commonly utilized coping method for coping strategies. This implied that education students intend to rely on social media to manage stress. By recognizing and adopting these coping mechanisms, students can enhance their overall well-being and build resilience in online learning environments. Understanding the specific problems that education students confront, as well as the coping techniques they use, is critical for designing targeted support systems and treatments to improve their academic experiences and mental well-being while learning online. Moreover, fostering a supportive online community among peers can further enhance students' ability to cope with the challenges of remote learning. Additionally, incorporating mindfulness practices into their daily routines can also contribute to students' overall well-being and resilience.

Keywords: *Adversities, Coping Mechanisms, Education Students, Online Learning*

Introduction:

Online learning has become a significant source of stress for students during the COVID-19 pandemic. Students face numerous inconveniences, deadlines, demands, and frustrations, which can be particularly stressful for those unfamiliar with many responsibilities. Higher education is a stressful period for students due to various reasons, such as living away from families, heavy syllabuses, and inefficiency in higher education. Adolescents are particularly vulnerable to academic stress due to the transitions at an individual and social level.

Communication in online learning settings is often asynchronous, leading to misunderstandings and escalating problems. Students face daily stressors such as living in a new environment, meeting new peers, dealing with personal issues, and academic pressures. Unexpected events in their families can also hinder their ability to focus on academic objectives. The pandemic has forced students to reconnect with teachers and fellow students via computers and cell phones, generating additional stressors that can lead to severe consequences in a teen's life.

Literature Review:

A great deal of the literature and research dealing with life events and stress during adolescence have cited school as a major contributor to student stress (Hattie & Russel, 2012). Stress has become part of students' academic life due to the various internal and external expectations placed upon their shoulders. Adolescents are particularly vulnerable to the problems associated with academic stress as transitions occur at an individual and social level what Alkenani (2022) cited that academic stress among students with learning difficulties is believed to result from meeting many academic requirements, for example, the school exam, answering questions in the classroom, and showing progress in school subjects, understanding the content that the teacher teaches, competing with his classmates, and fulfilling the academic expectations of teachers and parents; in addition to social problems, family problems, and problems surrounding them. This section of the paper will thematically discuss previously published literature related to academic

stress. Specifically, it will review subtopics associated with it. Now more than ever, there is a necessity for easily accessible school-wide interventions and services that can accommodate students' growing psychosocial challenges. This section of the paper will thematically discuss previously published literature related to academic stress.

Research Method:

The study used a descriptive quantitative design to investigate college students' characteristics and coping mechanisms during online learning. Data was collected through questionnaires and online surveys at Mandaue City College, a high-achieving institution. The sample size of 160 respondents was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan Table, based on a total population of 353 education students in the target school. Questions were adopted from studies by Apdol et al. (2021) and Bordios Jr. et al. (2022) but the reliability score was not disclosed. Ethical considerations were addressed, and efforts were made to ensure participant confidentiality and maximize response rates. The data collection process aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of students' experiences and coping strategies in online learning.

Findings and Discussion:

Status of Academic Stress

The outcomes of a study on the level of academic stress among college students were presented. It focused on three significant issues: academic workload, peer competition, and failure dread. The information gathered from the respondents is processed and given in tabular form, along with a descriptive discussion of the findings.

Table 2.
Academic Workload

STATEMENTS	WM	DE
The size of the curriculum/workload should be increased.	2.94	Often
Examinations are very stressful for me.	3.33	Always
I stay up late at night to finish my assignments.	2.87	Often
There are too many deadlines in school that take more work to meet.	2.73	Often
I struggle to do household tasks because I spend most of my time doing schoolwork online.	2.71	Often
Total Weighted Mean	2.92	Often

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Always (A), 2.51 – 3.25 – Often (O), 1.76 – 2.50 – Sometimes (S), 1.00 – 1.75 – Never (N), WM – Weighted Mean, DE – Descriptive Equivalent

The highest-rated statement is "Examinations are very stressful to me," with a weighted mean of 3.33, indicating that most respondents agree that exams cause significant stress. James (2016) discovered from the students' perspective that first-year undergraduates at an Australian university, despite their expertise with technology, lacked experience in the online learning setting. Worried about connectivity issues and technological problems. Whitelock (2006), who warns that system failure during an online exam can deter professors and students from utilizing such systems, discovered similar findings.

The statement with the lowest rating is "I find it difficult to do household tasks because I spend most of my time doing schoolwork online," with a weighted mean of 2.71, indicating that most respondents do not find it challenging to balance household tasks and schoolwork. Due to excessive schoolwork, students need help to do their household chores. Overall, the general weighted Mean of 2.92 indicates that respondents view their academic burden and stress as modest, while the size of the curriculum or workload is excessive. This emphasizes the need for educational institutions to find strategies to reduce academic stress and generate a more manageable student burden.

Table 3.
Peer Competition

STATEMENTS	WM	DE
The competitive attitude of my peers/classmates is quite intense.	2.35	Sometimes
My peers expect me to lead and take charge in group work.	2.25	Sometimes
My peers expect me to know the answer to complex questions.	2.36	Sometimes
My teachers rely on me to take control of group work.	1.86	Sometimes
My teachers are critical of my academic performance.	2.34	Sometimes
Total Weighted Mean	2.23	Sometimes

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Always (A), 2.51 – 3.25 – Often (O), 1.76 – 2.50 – Sometimes (S), 1.00 – 1.75 – Never (N), WM – Weighted Mean, DE – Descriptive Equivalent

Research has shown that a highly competitive atmosphere among peers can increase stress, anxiety, and adverse psychological outcomes. A study by Salmela-Aro and Tynkkyinen (2012) highlighted the association between intense peer competition and decreased academic engagement and motivation. A survey by Acedo et al. (2019) found that students who felt a solid expectation to lead in group work reported higher levels of self-efficacy and engagement. However, educators need to ensure that expectations are distributed fairly and that all students have opportunities to contribute and develop leadership skills. According to Peterson and Miller (2004) and Topping (2005), students will experience positive involvement in group work when they have appropriate skills for the task. Research suggests that excessive criticism from teachers is associated with increased stress, anxiety, and reduced self-esteem among students. Reinke et al. (2011) found that students who experienced high levels of teacher criticism exhibited lower academic engagement and motivation. The weighted Mean of 2.23 indicates that respondents experience relatively high peer competition in an academic context. These findings emphasize the importance of teachers being aware of their students' expectations and creating a supportive learning environment that supports collaboration while minimizing excessive peer competitiveness.

Table 4.
Fear of Failure

STATEMENTS	WM	DE
I feel discouraged if I get low test scores.	3	Often
I criticize myself more than I praise my achievements, even when it's well-deserved.	2.64	Often
I feel insecure if someone has higher scores than me.	1.92	Sometimes
As much as possible, I want to get the highest scores in class.	1.30	Never
My academic achievements are consistent.	2.43	Sometimes
Total Weighted Mean	2.26	Sometimes

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 – Never (N), 1.76 – 2.50 – Sometimes (S), 2.51 – 3.25 – Often (O), 3.26 – 4.00 – Always (A), WM – Weighted Mean, DE – Descriptive Equivalent

The table illustrated the results of a survey on students' fear of failure and self-criticism. The highest mean score was "I feel discouraged if I get low test scores," at 3, indicating that many students strongly agreed with this statement and are likely to experience feelings of discouragement when receiving low grades. Fear of failure develops gradually from the study of achievement motivation. Avoiding loss is an instinctive behavior of people. Birney et al. (1969) believe that fear of loss refers to the inner fear of an individual when they perceive that they may not achieve a specific goal. The fear of failure is the opposite of the desire to succeed and the motivation to avoid punishment for failure. For most people, fear of failure is uncontrollable. Individuals are often affected by the fear of failure and adopt the behavior of preventing achieving goals if they cannot be guaranteed success (Ajzen, 1991). Balkis and Duru (2012) showed that fear of failure and procrastination was associated with self-esteem. When they fail, those with weak self-esteem consider themselves to be defeated in their entirety, so they prefer to take no action for fear of failure. Haghbin et al. (2012) discovered a positive relationship between fear of failure and academic procrastination among students who feel less deserving and rightful.

"As much as possible, I want to get the highest scores in class" received the lowest mean score of 1.30, indicating that most students do not feel a strong need to outperform their classmates.

Table 5.
Status of Academic Stress

INDICATORS	WM	DE
Academic Overload	2.92	Often
Peer Competition	2.23	Sometimes
Fear of Failure	2.26	Sometimes

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Always (A), 2.51 – 3.25 – Often (O), 1.76 – 2.50 – Sometimes (S), 1.00 – 1.75 – Never (N), WM – Weighted Mean, DE – Descriptive Equivalent

The results showed that the participants experienced the highest levels of academic stress. Academic overload received the highest mean score of 2.92 out of the three types, indicating that participants felt the size of their curriculum or workload was excessive. Academic overload refers to students' excessive demands and pressures in their academic endeavors. Academic overload has been demonstrated in studies to have a negative impact on students' well-being, mental health, and academic performance. According to a survey conducted by Levecque et al. (2017), high levels of academic burden were connected with higher stress, burnout, and poor psychological well-being among students. Peer pressure is a typical occurrence in educational contexts, and it can have beneficial and harmful consequences for students. Moderate levels of peer competition can motivate students to excel academically and strive for higher achievements. On the other hand, intense or unhealthy peer competition can result in negative results such as increased stress, worry, and lower well-being. Ryan and Shim (2006) discovered that increased peer competitiveness was linked to decreased intrinsic motivation and interest in learning. Fear of failure is a psychological condition marked by anxiety or apprehension about failing to achieve scholastic expectations or experiencing unfavorable outcomes. Numerous studies have shown that students' academic performance and well-being suffer due to their fear of failure. Elliot and McGregor (2001) discovered that fear of failure might impair motivation, cause avoidance behaviors, and reduce academic engagement. Students afraid of failure are more likely to procrastinate, are perfectionists, and have low self-esteem.

Coping Mechanisms in Online Distance Learning

The outcomes of a study on the coping mechanisms among college students are presented in this section. It focuses on five major issues: peers, social media, psychological, family, and intrapersonal. The information gathered from the respondents is processed and given in tabular form, along with a descriptive discussion of the findings.

Table 6.

Peers

INDICATORS	WM	DE
I have been trying to find comfort with my friends.	3.28	Strongly Agree
Making time to call friends to catch up.	3.14	Agree
Stroll around with peers.	2.94	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.12	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree (SA), 2.51 – 3.25 – Agree (A), 1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree (D), 1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

The highest-rated statement is, "I have been trying to find comfort with my friends." It has the highest weighted Mean of 3.28, including that most respondents agreed that they find comfort with their friends through bonding (chit-chats, playing games, doing projects, and studying together) as their coping strategy. Learning with friends reduces stress; they will not feel pressured to do their schoolwork. They will be motivated to do their assignments, projects, and activities. Research suggested that peer support protects against depression, social anxiety (La Greca & Harrison, 2005), and test anxiety (Hoferichter & Raufelder, 2015). Suresh et al. (2021) list the few studies that have investigated peer support as a resource and summarize that, in general, peer support has been shown to improve the mental and physical health of students, including students' stress and burnout, although literature, and particularly multilevel approaches, is limited.

Single-level studies on the topic support the notation that peer support relates to increased academic involvement (Vargas-Madriz & Konishi, 2021) and academic achievement in Chemistry (Uzezi & Deya, 2017) and help students to pursue their educational goals (Patrick et al., 2004; Wentzel, 2005).

On the other hand, the lowest weighted Mean is 2.94, which is "Stroll around with peers." With these outcomes, students agree that they go along with their friends, even though they are pressured by their schoolwork. Sometimes, they bond and go to different places, despite their pending activities, assignments, etc.

Table 7.

Social Media

INDICATORS	WM	DE
I open my social media accounts, read updates, and sometimes scroll over shopping applications to comfort myself.	3.23	Agree
I find comfort when I watch videos (vlogs, funny videos, motivational videos) on YouTube.	3.37	Strongly Agree
I surf through social media platforms for motivational quotes.	3.07	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.22	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree (SA), 2.51 – 3.25 – Agree (A), 1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree (D), 1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

On the coping mechanisms of the education students in online distance learning, the item that gained the highest weighted Mean was the statement: I find comfort when I watch videos (vlogs, funny videos, motivational videos) on YouTube. Their agreement with this item means that they opt to surf videos on YouTube if they feel tired or stressed. This indicates that watching motivational videos, vlogs, etc., will help them relax and reprocess their thinking. This result finds congruence in the study. People choose to spend more time on the knowledge that is relevant to successfully managing life's stressful areas, according to research by Knobloch-Westerwick et al. (2009). Both indicate that individuals approach or characterize problems using the media as a coping mechanism.

A substantial body of work has explored media usage as a means of escapism about emotion-focused coping (e.g., Katz and Foulkes, 1962; Halfmann & Reinecke, 2021). Such a study indicates that media exposure is regularly utilized to seek distraction from dissatisfaction, stress, and anxiety in daily life (e.g., Kubey and Csikszentmihalyi, 1990; Moskalenko & Heine, 2003). Other conceptualizations suggest that escapism through media use can be a short-term functional strategy in that it may temporarily help the person reduce stress and anxiety and prepare for subsequent problem-focused coping attempts. Escapist media use is frequently discussed as a dysfunctional coping strategy, similar to avoidance-oriented and emotion-focused coping (e.g., Meier et al., 2018). Nonetheless, table 2, with the statement "I surf through social media platforms for motivational quotes." gets the lowest weighted Mean of 3.07 and a descriptive equivalent of "agree." With these results, students often surf for motivational quotes to reduce their stress, motivate them, and encourage them to continue despite their struggles.

Table 8.

Psychological

INDICATORS	WM	DE
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Get enough (sufficient) sleep.	2.60	Agree
Have a healthy diet.	2.55	Agree
Go for a walk and breathe fresh air.	2.97	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	2.71	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree (SA), 2.51 – 3.25 – Agree (A), 1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree (D), 1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

The weighted mean scores of the student's responses are shown in this table. The highest mean score is for "Go for a walk and breathe fresh air," with a score of 2.97, indicating that this strategy is perceived to be effective in managing stress. The second and third highest scores are for "Get enough (sufficient) sleep" and "Have a healthy diet," respectively, suggesting that students recognize the importance of taking care of their physical health in reducing stress. Numerous studies have found that not getting enough sleep hurts cognitive functioning, mood control, immunological function, and overall health. For example, Hirshkowitz et al. (2015) found a link between poor sleep and an increased risk of chronic illnesses such as obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and mental health disorders. A balanced diet's impact on general health and well-being is well-proven in scientific literature. Consuming a balanced and healthy diet has been proven to improve physical health, mental well-being, cognitive function, and disease prevention. A comprehensive review conducted by O'Neil et al. (2014), for example, indicates the benefits of a nutritious diet, such as lower risk of obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and improved mental health outcomes. Spending time in nature and engaging in activities such as walking, running, or hiking have been shown to reduce stress, increase mood, improve cognitive performance, and boost overall psychological well-being. Thompson Coon et al. (2011), for example, found that exposure to natural areas is connected with better mental health outcomes such as lower stress and improved mood.

The general weighted mean score for all the strategies is 2.71, which indicates that the students generally perceive these strategies to help manage stress related to online distance learning.

Table 9.
 Family

INDICATORS	WM	DE
I have time with my family to lessen the stress that I experience from online distance learning.	2.84	Agree
Have a heart-to-heart talk with family at dinner time (quality time).	2.66	Agree
Have family activities (Play board games, do an art project, or walk).	2.43	Disagree
Total Weighted Mean	2.64	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree (SA), 2.51 – 3.25 – Agree (A), 1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree (D), 1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

This table pertained to the respondents' coping mechanisms in dealing with stress from online distance learning about their family. The results show that having time with their family to lessen the stress they experience from online distance learning has a weighted mean of 2.84, indicating that it is an effective coping mechanism for the respondents. Having heart-to-heart talks with their family during dinner time, another coping mechanism, also has a weighted mean of 2.66. On the other hand, having family activities, such as playing board games, doing an art project, or going for a walk, has a lower weighted mean of 2.43, indicating that it is a less effective coping mechanism for the respondents. According to research, participating in activities and interactions with family members can help with a sense of belonging, emotional well-being, and stress relief. Chen and colleagues (2018) discovered that family support and coherence were essential predictors of lower stress levels among students in their study. Quality time spent with family members creates a supportive environment where people can voice their problems and seek comfort, thereby reducing the stress associated with online distance learning. Heart-to-heart conversations with family members, especially over shared mealtimes, provide an opportunity for genuine dialogue and emotional connection. According to Fiese and colleagues (2002), family mealtimes positively impact children's well-being and family ties. Meaningful dinner conversations allow family members to communicate their views, emotions, and worries, resulting in improved emotional support and a sense of togetherness. Engaging in family activities such as board games, art projects, or walking together can effectively cope with the stress associated with online distance learning. According to research, engaging in fun activities as a family improves happy emotions, strengthens family togetherness, and reduces stress levels. Gadermann and colleagues (2019) discovered that participating in shared leisure activities positively correlates with family functioning and well-being. Family activities provide relaxation, humor, and connection, which can help people cope with the stress and obstacles of online distance learning. Overall, the general weighted Mean for coping mechanisms related to family is 2.64, which indicates that the respondents find coping mechanisms related to family relatively effective in managing their stress.

Table 10.
Intrapersonal

INDICATORS	WM	DE
I do some physical activities or exercises to lessen the stress I feel.	2.87	Agree
I have been praying or meditating whenever I feel tired and stressed.	3.36	Strongly Agree
I have been doing something to think about it less, such as going to movies, watching TV, reading books, and sleeping.	3.38	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.20	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree (SA), 2.51 – 3.25 – Agree (A), 1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree (D), 1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

On the coping mechanisms of the education students in online learning, the item that gained the highest Mean was the statement: *I have been doing something to think about it less, such as going to movies, watching TV, reading books, and sleeping.* With a result of 3.38, the students find comfort in doing something that will relax or refresh their minds. Also, reading books, watching videos, and watching movies are my time for the students. Additionally, sleeping is essential for students to relax their minds. Activities like going to the movies, watching TV, reading books, and sleeping can distract from overthinking and reduce stress. These activities can aid people in diverting their attention from their concerns and offering a little respite from their issues, according to Johnson, J. G. et al. (2019).

Based on studies, viewing movies or TV episodes can improve mental health by lessening the symptoms of anxiety and despair. A study found that reading books can reduce stress and improve general well-being (2013). Furthermore, enough sleep is vital for maintaining mental health since it can make people feel refreshed and energized, which helps reduce stress and overthinking.

Based on this table, the lowest weighted Mean is 2.87 with a descriptive equivalent of "agree," corresponding to the statement, "I do some physical activities or exercises to lessen the stress I feel." This indicates that the respondents agree with this statement and often do physical activities because others may not find it their coping mechanism or do not have enough time to do physical activities.

Table 11.
Coping Mechanisms in Online Learning

INDICATORS	WM	DE
Peers	3.12	Agree
Social Media	3.22	Agree
Psychological	2.71	Agree
Family	2.64	Agree
Intrapersonal	3.20	Agree

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 – Strongly Agree (SA), 2.51 – 3.25 – Agree (A), 1.76 – 2.50 – Disagree (D), 1.00 – 1.75 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

Based on the table, the highest category is social media, with a score of 3.22, which suggests that social media usage also considerably impacts mental health. Social networks enable people to connect and reconnect with others by removing barriers of time and distance, whether it is through official online class attendance or casual conversation on social media (Antoci A. et al. 2015), (Hall J.A. et al., 2018), (Barasa E. et al. 2018). For all of these factors, students can become significantly more resilient in times of crisis by using online platforms. Students are safeguarded from the possible risks of despair, tension, and anxiety that people typically experience during an emergency situation by using social media and taking online classes. People's well-being is also improved by these platforms (Barasa E. et al. 2018). Furthermore, research has given empirical evidence of the benefits of online communication as a social, economic, and health supplement to face-to-face encounters (Antoci A. et al. 2015). With ratings of 2.64, family relationships and psychological issues got lower rankings but are still considered essential elements in respondents' mental health.

Conclusion:

Academic overload, particularly exams, was the leading cause of stress among the participants, making it the most evident stressor. Although it was nevertheless a factor, peer competition seemed to have less of an impact than academic pressure and failure-related anxiety. Social media appeared as the most significant category for coping strategies, with individuals finding comfort in watching various types of videos on websites like YouTube. Even though the weighted mean ratings for family relationships and psychological factors were significantly reduced, they were nonetheless acknowledged as significant contributing factors to the participants' mental health.

References:

Abdullah, Dr. R. (2022). Academic Stress. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33193/IJoHSS.30.2022.375>

Antoci A., Sabatini F., Sodini M. Online and offline social participation and social poverty traps: Can social networks save human relations? J. Math. Sociol. 2015;39:229– 256. doi: 10.1080/0022250X.2015.1022278.

Barasa E., Mbau R., Gilson L. What Is Resilience and How Can it Be Nurtured? A Systematic Review of Empirical Literature on Organizational Resilience. Int. J.Health Policy Manag. 2018;7:491–503. doi: 10.15171/ijhpm.2018.06.

Bulo, J.G. & M.G. Sanchez (2014). Sources of Stress Among College Students. CVCITC Research Journal, 1 (1), pp 16-25.

Jones, RW., & Hattie, JA., (2012). Academic Stress amongst Adolescents: An Examination by Ethnicity, Grade, and Sex.

Shastri, S., and Veena, N. (2012). Stress and Academic Performance. DOI: 10.25215/0303.068. Sincero, S. M. (n.d.). Stress and Cognitive Appraisal - Lazarus and Folkman. Stress and Cognitive Appraisal - Lazarus and Folkman.

Junling Li, and Wanyu Che., (2022). Challenges and Coping strategies of online learning for college students in the context of COVID-19: A survey of Chinese universities, Sustainable Cities and Society, Volume 83, 2022, 103958, ISSN 2210-6707, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2022.103958>

Research Instrument

The researchers used an adopted survey from Part I-II. Taken from Bordios, et al and Apdol, et al. The study utilizes two parts of the questionnaire using close-ended questions. Part I is the status of academic stress. Part II is about the coping mechanisms in online distance learning. There were fifteen (15) questions for academic stress, and fifteen (15) questions for coping mechanisms. In Part I, the respondents were asked to rate each question using a four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 4: 4 – Always; 3 – Often; 2- Sometimes; 1 – Never. In Part II the respondents were asked to rate each question using a four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 4: 4 – Strongly Agree; 3 – Agree; 2 – Disagree; 1 – Strongly Disagree.

Part I: Status of academic stress (Apdol et al. 2021)

Directions: Please read each statement carefully and check the box that corresponds to your answer. Kindly refer to the scale below.

4 – Always (A) 3 – Often (O) 2 – Sometimes (S) 1 – Never (N)

ACADEMIC OVERLOAD	4 A	3 O	2 S	1 N
1. The size of the curriculum/workload is excessive.				
2. Examinations are very stressful to me.				
3. I stay up late at night just to finish my assignments.				
4. There are too many deadlines in school that are difficult to meet.				
5. I find it difficult to do household tasks because I spend most of my time doing schoolwork online.				
PEER COMPETITION				
6. The competitive attitude of my peers/classmates is quite intense.				
7. My peers expect me to lead and take charge in group work.				
8. My peers expect me to know the answer to difficult questions				
9. My teachers rely on me to take charge in group work.				
10. My teachers are critical of my academic performance.				
FEAR OF FAILURE				
11. I feel discouraged if I get low test scores.				
12. I criticize myself more than I praise my achievements, even when it's well-deserved.				
13. I feel insecure if someone has higher scores than me.				
14. As much as possible, I want to get the highest scores in class.				
15. My academic achievements are consistent.				

Part II: Coping mechanisms in online distance learning.

Directions: Listed below are statements about level of stress and coping mechanisms. Please indicate how strongly you agree or disagree with each statement by putting a check mark. Survey questionnaire was taken from **Bordios Jr. et al. (2022)**.

4 – Strongly Agree (SA) 3 – Agree (A) 2 – Disagree (D) 1- Strongly Disagree (SD)

	4 SA	3 A	2 D	1 SD
PEERS				
1. I've been trying to find comfort with my friends.				
2. Making time to call friends to catch up				
3. Stroll around with peers.				
SOCIAL				
4. I open my social media accounts, read updates, and sometimes scroll over shopping applications to comfort myself.				
5. I find comfort when I watch videos (vlogs, funny videos, motivational videos) on YouTube.				
6. I surf through social media platforms for motivational quotes.				
PSYCHOLOGICAL				
7. Get enough (sufficient) sleep.				
8. Have a healthy diet.				
9. Go for a walk and breathe fresh air.				
FAMILY				
10. I have time with my family to lessen the stress that I experience from online distance learning.				
11. Have a heart-to-heart talk with family at dinner time (quality time).				
12. Have family activities (Play board games, do an art project, or go for a walk.)				
INTRAPERSONAL				
13. I do some physical activities or exercises to lessen the stress I feel.				
14. I've been praying or meditating whenever I feel tired and stressed.				
15. I've been doing something to think about it less, such as going to movies, watching TV, reading books, and sleeping.				

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The research entitled “**Adversities and Coping Mechanism of Education Students During Online Learning**” prepared and submitted by Janyne Paracuelles, Marmae Piano, Christine Joy Linao, Renlie Roes Escobar, Erica Tayactac, Hannie Chritine Josol , has been thoroughly read and corrected by me as the Research Censor and the manuscript has been edited by the student-researchers.

After compliance with the comments and suggestions given, they have made revisions which are now considered to meet the standard for a quality research output.

PHILADELFA E. VESTAL -RGC, ED.D.
College Research Coordinator
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CERTIFICATION FOR GRAMMAR CHECK

Name of Grammarian: Joseph Arnold Baunsit

Highest Educational Attainment: Bachelor of Secondary Education – Social Science

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This is to certify that the study entitled "Adversities and Coping Mechanism of Education Students During Online Learning" of Janyne S. Paracuelles, Marmae M. Piano, Christen Joy B. Linao, Renlie Roes R. Escobar, Erica A. Tayactac, Hannie Christine A. Josol, Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in English students of Mandaue City College has been checked by Grammarly Apps and was reviewed by Joseph Arnold C. Baunsit as Grammarian.

This certification is issued upon request of the group as part of their oral defense requirements.
Given this 28th day of June 2023.

MR. JOSEPH ARNOLD P. BAUNSIT

Signature over the printed name
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